

SOME ASPECTS OF PROVIDING INFORMATION- PSYCHOLOGICAL SECURITY

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Abstract. *This article describes the rapidly developing information field, various risks encountered in it, and some issues of ensuring information-psychological security, as well as the concept of information-psychological security and its principles.*

Keywords: *information, information security, information threat, information-psychological security, Internet, manipulation, confidentiality, openness, integrity of information resources.*

Today, modern information technologies are gaining importance in forming the intellectual potential of the information society. The educational process is conducted on the basis of information, social life is managed effectively. Nowadays, it is impossible to imagine any sphere of life without information.

Today, we live in a rapidly changing, intense and at the same time extremely complex time, which is radically different from the times that humanity has experienced so far. Experts call this rapid period "mass information" or "globalization age".

That's why the whole world is informed about the event that happened in some corner of the earth in a few seconds. This undoubtedly indicates that the role and role of the press and mass media is increasing. In this sense, any press should fully, objectively and truthfully reflect the events, changes, and updates happening in society. As we set ourselves the task of building an open and free democratic society in our country, I think that in the first place, we should develop ways to protect ourselves from information attacks, and each of us should show real courage in this way. It is important to enrich the spiritual world of our people, to prevent the emergence of a spiritual vacuum, to establish ideological immunity, to protect against information attacks. For this, first of all, it is necessary to establish a healthy way of life in the minds and hearts of young people, who are the strong foundations of the development of our country, to form in them a sense of pride in their history, and to inculcate good qualities such as respect for national and national values.

Information security means the level of protection of the information space, which ensures the basic formation and development of society, people, organizations and state interests. An information threat is a factor or group of factors that threaten the functioning of the information space of society [1].

The concept of information and psychological security means effective use of all available information resources in order to protect society, its individual groups and individuals from the negative effects of destructive forms and types of information. Information-psychological security in the information and information given in the mass media is intellectual reduction, ignorance and naivety, binding people, aggressive advertising, as well as open and covert brutality and use of force, drug addiction, alcoholism, toxicomania, anti-social behavior, nationalism, racism, requires that there be no signs of religious, class discrimination and intolerance.

The main principles of information security are as follows:

Openness is a quality that can be consumed at the request of a representative and implies universality.

Confidentiality is a property that restricts access to information or its disclosure to outsiders, organizations, or processes.

Negative information-psychological security means influencing a person or a group of persons using special means and methods of influencing the human psyche, causing negative consequences for the individual, society and the state.

Negative information-psychological security effects are manifested in:

- Damage to human health;
- Unconsciously blocking Jesus' freedom of expression, artificially instilling in him the syndrome of dependence;
- Man's loss of political, cultural, moral self-identification;
- Manipulation of social consciousness.

The means of information-psychological security are as follows:

1) Special influence tools — technical and software tools used to exert a negative informational and psychological influence on a person or a group of persons.

2) Special methods of influence - the sequence and duration of methods of influencing the human psyche, the consequences of which lead to negative results for the individual, society and the state.

Information is defined as a message or information about specific events, which has been used since ancient times to explain, understand and perceive them, and which has acquired a new, broader meaning later due to the development of cybernetics and informatics.

Technical, software, algorithmic works and their organizational tools are of incomparable importance in the collection, storage, systematization and public use of information for a specific purpose. Every link of the information society refers to the information bank, and on this basis, modern educational technologies are created and the possibility of optimal management of educational processes is created.

As we pay attention to the social and political changes taking place in the life of our society, which is on the path of independent development, one of the issues that are directly affecting the destiny of the country, that is, the issue of protecting the population from information and psychological attacks, is considered as one of the most urgent problems.

We can indicate the following as the main goals of the country in ensuring information security:

- protection of national interests in the conditions of the increasing globalization of many information processes, the formation of world information networks, and the development of developed countries for dominance in the information space;

- to create opportunities for state authorities and management bodies, organizations, and enterprises to obtain the information necessary for the activities of citizens in full and without any obstacles;

- integrity of information resources, prevention of violations and illegal use, etc.

In the near future, as a result of the further expansion of the globalization process, with the transition of world countries to an informational way of life, this issue will inevitably become more urgent.

In order to positively solve this issue, a number of measures should be taken. In particular, it is necessary to create a strong legal framework that ensures the information security of the individual, society and the state, to form mechanisms for their practical operation and legal bases that can resist information attacks, and to conduct special measures aimed at ensuring information security in state administration and local self-government bodies. It is also very important to create strong, special knowledge in order to increase the culture of working with information among young people, to improve their skills in receiving, processing, and storing information.

In fact, we are witnessing that Uzbekistan has attracted the attention of several developed countries in a historically short period of time. This is evidenced by our many achievements in education, economy, sports and other similar fields. It is worth noting that in such a place where growth, development, and development take root, there will certainly appear forces that encourage members of society to spiritual decline, spiritual crises, spiritual poverty, and various base actions. For example, you cannot imagine our life today without the Internet. Because the above-mentioned field includes a very large information capacity, from which we have the opportunity to receive various information, information, and news in convenient and fast conditions. But there is another important and at the same time most urgent aspect of the issue, which is that the general public, especially the young people who are just growing up and are still prone to emotional changes, can use the Internet and other modern telecommunication technologies to improve their spirituality, enlightenment, morals, and education. the fact that it has a negative impact on education is shocking.

In conclusion, in order for the Internet to enter the field of education and its use in the educational process, we must form certain skills in the minds of our young people. In particular, pedagogues should take into account the following aspects when using mass media in the process of forming a student's personality:

- to mentally prepare and guide students to read, learn and effectively use mass media materials;
- formation of moral-ethical, social-political, legal worldview in the students, correct positive attitude towards mass media materials;
- providing explanations for the correct perception of mass media materials;
- parents should also help young people to analyze media materials correctly and develop skills as free and independent thinkers in the process of family education.

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